

ABSORPTION AND FLUORESCENCE SPECTRA OF BENZYLIDENE-COUMARANONES

By S. K. K. JATKAR AND B. N. MATTOO

Absorption and fluorescence spectra of 4'-methoxy- and 4'-benzyloxy-benzylidene coumaranones have been reported and discussed. Effect of various substitutions has been studied.

Though strong fluorescence is met with in the solid state, the efficiency is low in solution. There is an appreciable 'inner-filter' effect.

Absorption spectrum of coumaran, reported by Jones and Lin Isay (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1836), shows one band beyond $2,000\text{\AA}$, having fine structure ($282, 289\text{m}\mu$). Some coumaranone or coumaran-3-one derivatives have been studied by Smith and Boyack (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2687). The spectrum of 2-isopropyl-4 : 6 : 7-trimethyl derivative, for instance, shows two bands beyond $2,000\text{\AA}$, viz., $287\text{ m}\mu$ and $260\text{ m}\mu$.

Substitution of a $=\text{CH}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ group in 2-position in coumaranone, which is in conjugation with $\text{C}=\text{O}$, changes the spectrum altogether, as expected. Now the benzylidene-coumaranone (e.g. 6:7-dimethoxy-3'-amino) shows two bands at $252\text{ m}\mu$ and $310\text{ m}\mu$ (cf. Price *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1934, 56, 2483). The $-\text{NH}_2$ group in 3'-position, as in the above example, cannot produce such additional resonance, as when in 4'-position. Thus, the isomeric compound, 6:7-dimethoxy-4'-amino derivative shows bands at $257\text{ m}\mu$ and $445\text{ m}\mu$. There is, however, a broad shoulder on the short-wave side of the $445\text{ m}\mu$ band. The absorption has now shifted right into the blue end of the visible, because of high electron-donating capacity of $-\text{NH}_2$. As the resonance theory of colour (Bury, *ibid.*, 1935, 57, 2115) was not proposed when Price *et al.* studied the absorption spectra of the *p*- and *m*-aminobenzylidene-coumaranones, their doubts about such a large difference in absorption spectrum by changing $-\text{NH}_2$ from 3'- to 4'- position were not unjustified.

No work on the fluorescence of benzylidene-coumaranones is reported so far.

The present work on fluorescence and absorption of these compounds is discussed below; the data are graphically represented in Figs. 1 and 2.

Absorption.—The resonance in coumaranone will be mainly of the type :

Substitution of benzylidene group in 2-position will increase the resonance and the following dipolar structures will contribute appreciably to the excited state resonance hybrid :

Resonance of the type (III) will be inhibited by electron-donating groups present in 4'-position. As the present study includes benzylidene-coumaranones with *para* OCH_3 OR substitution, we may not consider the resonance of the type (III).

In *p*-methoxybenzylidene-coumaranone or 4'-methoxybenzylidene-coumaranone, the resonance of the type (II) will be appreciably increased.

Thus, we find its absorption spectrum extending right into the visible, with strongest maximum at $403 \text{ m}\mu$ ($\epsilon = 28,500$). The other maxima include those at 540 (very broad and weak), 342 , 256 and $225 \text{ m}\mu$ with $\epsilon = 780$, 14760 , 15540 and 9040 respectively. The integrated absorption $\int \epsilon d\nu$ (76.0) is not very much different from that of the corresponding isomeric (4'- OCH_3) flavone (74.5).

Introduction of 5-Me or 7-Me groups was found to produce a slight bathochromic shift in longest-wave absorption band ($\Delta\lambda = 5 \text{ m}\mu$ and $3 \text{ m}\mu$ respectively). Slightly lower values of $\int \epsilon d\nu$ of the Me-substituted derivatives, and appreciably lower ϵ_{max} values in the $4,000 \text{ \AA}$ band first gave rise to doubts about the purity of the 4'-methoxy derivative, but the values were confirmed after repeating the measurements with a re-purified sample. The unusual behaviour of alkyl groups in this case is not clear at present.

Substitution of 6-Me, 3'- OCH_3 , 4'-benzyloxy groups in benzylidene-coumaranone changes the nature of the spectrum in the high-frequency region; absorption in the longest-wave band being little affected. Thus, it shows absorption bands at 405 , 330 , 275 and $255 \text{ m}\mu$.

Fluorescence.—Though benzylidene-coumaranones were found to emit brilliant green fluorescence in solid state, when examined under a Wood's lamp, these in solution emit only feeble blue fluorescence. Qualitative comparison of relative efficiencies with the isomeric flavones is not possible with the data collected, as the absorption spectra are radically different and taking the spectral distribution in the exciting radiation into consideration is very essential.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

4'-Methoxybenzylidene-coumaranones have a blue emission (4,200-5,600Å) with maxima in the region of 4,700Å. The emission will be affected by the 'inner-filter' effect of the unexcited molecules because of their appreciable absorption in the blue region. The 6-methyl-3'-methoxy-4'-benzyloxy analogue has a much greater efficiency ($I_f/dv = 89.0$, relative $fFdv = 2,130$ as compared to 76.0 and 200 respectively for 4'-OCH₃ analogue, and its λ_{max}^p is also red-shifted to 515 m μ ($\Delta\lambda = 40$ m μ), shown also by the change in colour of the emission to green. The effect of such substituents as 6-methyl, 3'-methoxy or 7:3'-dimethoxy group in 4'-benzyloxybenzylidene-coumaranones in causing large increase in efficiency, is also common to the corresponding flavones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Absorption measurements were done with a Beckman DU spectrophotometer and fluorescence spectra obtained with a spectrofluorimeter (cf. Jatkar and Mattoo, *J. Univ. Poona*, 1954, No. 6, 67).

Absorption spectra have been measured in aqueous alcohol (87%), in neutral, $10^{-4}N$ -HCl and $10^{-4}N$ -KOH solutions, while fluorescence was studied in alcoholic (96%) solution; concentration = $0.5 \times 10^{-4}M$. Integrated absorption (2,100-5,000Å) and fluorescence were computed from the areas of the respective spectral curves (v -scale), measured planimetrically. For a qualitative comparison of fluorescence efficiencies, the spectral distribution of the exciting radiation has not been taken into account.

The compounds used were pure as judged by their m.p.'s.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
POONA UNIVERSITY,
POONA 7.

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